

Evidence Gap Maps — GLP-1 Receptor Agonists in Adults with Obesity

Systematic mapping of randomised controlled trial evidence across intervention agents, outcome domains, and trial phases.
Bubble size is directly proportional to the number of eligible RCTs per cell per phase. Empty cells indicate absolute evidence gaps.

Phase 2 Phase 3 Phase 4 | Bubble size ∝ number of RCTs (continuous) | Grey dot = Absolute evidence gap | Illustrative Data — Final counts from Level 5 Extraction

Figure 2a — Evidence Gap Map: Efficacy Outcomes of GLP-1 Receptor Agonists in Adults with Obesity

Y-axis: Intervention agents. X-axis: Efficacy outcome domains and sub-outcomes. Each cell displays up to three bubbles (one per trial phase); bubble diameter is directly proportional to the number of eligible RCTs reporting that outcome. All data are illustrative.

Figure 2b — Evidence Gap Map: Safety Outcomes of GLP-1 Receptor Agonists in Adults with Obesity

Y-axis: Intervention agents. X-axis: Safety outcome domains and sub-outcomes. Each cell displays up to three bubbles (one per trial phase); bubble diameter is directly proportional to the number of eligible RCTs reporting that outcome. All data are illustrative.

Note. Bubble diameter is directly and continuously proportional to the number of eligible RCTs per cell per phase (scale: diameter = 10 + (n - 1) × 3 px, max 46 px). All counts are illustrative; final values will be derived from Level 5 (Outcome Characteristics) extraction within the CAMA hierarchical data collection framework.
Phase colour coding: Blue = Phase 2 | Teal = Phase 3 | Orange = Phase 4 | Grey dot = Absolute evidence gap (no eligible RCTs identified).